

Seed treatment to maintain viability, vigor, and yield potential of stored rice seed

R. N. Basu and P. Pal, College of Agriculture, University of Calcutta, Calcutta 700 019, India

Rice seed deteriorate significantly under ordinary uncontrolled storage in eastern India, especially during the warm and humid monsoon months from June to September. Studies at the Calcutta University College of Agriculture over the past 5 years have led to the development of a simple and easily practiced soaking-drying method of seed treatment to maintain vigor, viability, and productivity. Before stored seed begin to lose viability (5–10 months, depending on ambient conditions), they are soaked in double their volume of water or dilute solutions of sodium phosphate (dibasic, 10^{-4} M) for 5 hours and then dried back to their original weight in the sun or in a current of hot air (36–38°C) in a drying cabinet. The treatment greatly minimized the subsequent deterioration of such seeds when restored under ambient conditions (see table).

With fresh seed, the soaking-drying treatment is ineffective and would even accelerate deterioration when seed are stored for longer periods. But the treatment would break the dormancy of freshly harvested seed of certain cultivars

Effect of different physiochemical seed treatments on germination and yield of rice.^a University of Calcutta, India.

Treatment ^b	Germination ^c (%)	Mean root length after 120 h (mm)	Mean shoot length after 120 h (mm)	Grain yield ^d (t/ha)
Control	68 b	52 b	15 b	4.6 c
Water	88 a	62 a	23 a	6.1 b
Sodium phosphate (dibasic, 10^{-4} M)	91 a	66 a	25 a	6.7 a

^aIn any column, means that are followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^bNine-month-old Ratna seed, which had been stored under ambient conditions (RH $67 \pm 11\%$, temp. $27.1 \pm 4^\circ\text{C}$), were treated on 22 Aug. 1976 and were subsequently sown in Dec. 1976.

^cGermination tests were conducted in the laboratory at 28°C before sowing in the seedbed on 21 Dec. 1976.

^dYield of crop at 135 days' duration (sowing to transplanting, 40 days; transplanting to harvest, 95 days); differences in field (nursery) emergence of seedlings were eliminated during transplanting.

and give more uniform germination of seed that are immediately planted. Treatment of old, deteriorating seed is not advisable. The marginal effects of presowing treatment of stored seeds imply the necessity of maintaining a sufficient time gap between treatment and planting.

Hydration has also been achieved by spraying or dipping the stored seed in water or chemical solutions for a few minutes and then keeping them in shade 2–3 hours before drying. Even equilibrating the moisture of stored seed with a saturated atmosphere (100% RH) for 24 hours, then drying them back,

would greatly reduce seed deterioration in subsequent storage. Drying back to the original weight is important; storage of partially dried seed would do more harm than good. Seed that have been treated can be re-treated several months later to further extend their storage life.

The treatments have been effective in all rice cultivars so far studied: Ratna, Jaya, IR8, Pusa 2-21, Mahsuri, Rupsail, Patnai 23, Sitabhog, Dular, and Dhairal. The method could be used to maintain germplasm collections under ordinary storage conditions for a considerable period, and eliminates the need to regrow the genetic stocks each year. **W**

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Varietal reaction to *Podredumbre de la Vaim* (*Ophiobolus* sp.) in Lambayeque, Peru

Oscar Ojeda Ch. and Alberto Jimenez S. Lambayeque, Peru

Twenty-five-day-old seedlings of the varieties Nylamp, Chicama, Minabir, Inti, IR8, Siam Garden, Mochica, and Chancay were inoculated with a mycelium suspension of *Ophiobolus* sp in such a way that the mycelium was in contact with the sheaths. The plants were then

kept in a greenhouse for 2 months. Adequate humidity was provided by irrigating the plants as needed. The presence or absence of typical disease symptoms and fungus structures was then evaluated.

The sheaths of Nylamp, Mochica, and Siam Garden varieties were all infected but Chicama, Minabit, and Chancay had only 25% sheath infection. Inti and IR8 were infected least, suggesting varietal resistance to the disease in Lambayeque state, Peru. **W**

Varietal reaction to kresek infection

T. W. Mew, associate plant pathologist, C. M. Vera Cruz and R. C. Reyes, research aides, International Rice Research Institute

Kresek is normally observed 1 to 4 weeks after transplanting. Adult plants may also be infected if conditions are favorable for the disease and if the variety is susceptible. Under experimental conditions, young seedlings are infected more than older seedlings.

IR8, which has no gene for bacterial blight resistance, and IR1545, which has a recessive gene (*xa5*), were further evaluated for response to kresek infection at different ages. Plants were inoculated by dipping their roots in bacterial suspension for 5 minutes. All IR8 seedlings were infected at ages ranging from 9 to 32 days after seeding (DS). At 9 and 16 DS, IR1545 was as susceptible as IR8. But at 23 DS, 54% of the IR1545 plants were infected with kresek, and at 32 DS, 8% were infected. That indicates that kresek resistance is expressed not only between varieties but also within varieties at different ages.

When IR8, IR20, IR1545, and DV85, which differ in resistance to bacterial blight, were tested for kresek infection by the root-dipping method of inoculation with Pxo82, DV85 was infected less than the others. IR8, IR20, and IR1545 also differed in response to kresek at different inoculum concentrations.

Fourteen varieties were then evaluated in the greenhouse and in the field for kresek reaction against two isolates, Pxo61 and Pxo82. The varieties varied in reaction to the two isolates. In addition, the reactions of Ketan Lumba, Lakshini Lumba, IR8 (susceptible check),

and India Dular (resistant check) to the three Philippine pathotypes of *X. oryzae* for leaf blight indicated that their kresek reactions did not correlate with their leaf blight reactions.

On the basis of overall reaction to the two isolates in the greenhouse, India Dular was ranked as most resistant; the susceptible check IR8 ranked 13th of the 14 varieties. In the field test with the same inoculation method, India Dular was most resistant and IR8, most susceptible. Plants were scored at 21 days after inoculation in the greenhouse and at 6 weeks in the field. **W**

Scoring for varietal resistance to kresek

T. W. Mew, associate plant pathologist, C. M. Vera Cruz and R. C. Reyes, research aides, International Rice Research Institute

Because kresek is a systemic infection of bacterial blight, the scoring of infection at a certain time after inoculation should be standardized. In a preliminary greenhouse test, the percentage of kresek development was found to climax 3 to 4 weeks after inoculation by the root-dipping method. Experiments using IR8 were thus designed to determine the proper number of plants to serve as bases

for varietal testing and screening, and the optimal number of days after inoculation for scoring. Obviously, the higher the number of plants, the lower the coefficient of variation obtained on the basis of estimated standard error of the means. This holds true for the prolonged duration of infection after inoculation. For practical purposes, from 60 to 80 plants scored at any time from 21 to 24 days (C.V. = 13%) after inoculation seem adequate for greenhouse tests. In the field, a proper base is 100 hills/variety scored at the 5th week after artificial inoculation and transplanting. **W**

rows in wooden boxes. A susceptible check, Taichung Native 1 (TN1), was planted as a border. At 1 week after sowing, the wooden boxes were transferred to a galvanized iron tray filled with water. Brown planthoppers that had been raised on TN1 were transferred to the seedlings. (The original source of the hoppers was a collection

Reaction of varieties to brown planthopper in the laboratory. Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, India.

Designation	Origin	Damage rating ^a
Nira	USA	0
Aruvatham chormali	Malabar	1
Thone-lone-lon B.20	Burma	1
Morada	South Canara	1
Co 10	Tamil Nadu	1
ASD 11	Tamil Nadu	1
Arupatham Kuruvai	Coimbatore	3
Kuruvai kalyan	Tirunelveli	3
Moshanam	Chinglepet	3
Mutha samba	South Arcot	3
Velan samba	South Arcot	3
Ptb 15	Kerala	3
Ratna chooda	Ganjam	3
Gurida Akkalu	Ganjam	3
Menthi Bayahenda	Ganjam	3
Chennagi	Bellary	3
Seera Samba		
wild paddy	Sri Lanka	3
Bing Yang Chao	China	3
Changalisein	China	3
Itach-huning	China	3
Talichao	China	3
Glutinous variety	Burma	3

^aOn a scale of 1 to 9: 0 = immune; 9 = very susceptible.

Reaction of wild rice species to sheath blight

S. Kannaiyan and N. N. Prasad, Microbiology Laboratory, Agriculture College, Annamalai University, Annamalai nagar 608101, Tamil Nadu, India

Ten strains of wild species were raised in mud pots and inoculated with the sheath blight pathogen *Rhizoctonia solani* by the straw bit method. Their disease reactions were observed and recorded. *Oryza australiensis* and *O. nivara* were highly susceptible to the disease but *O. rufipogon* and *O. barthii* were resistant. The other wild rices were susceptible. **W**

Nira, a brown planthopper-resistant variety

M. Balasubramanian, M. Mohanasundaram, R. Velusamy, P. V. Subba Rao, and I. P. Janaki, Department of Agricultural Entomology, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 3, Tamil Nadu, India

During 1976 kharif and rabi, and 1977 kharif, the resistance to brown planthopper and stem borer of 844 bulk progenies, 804 single-plant selections, 988 germplasm entries, and 62 varieties were evaluated in the laboratory and in the field.

From 30 to 40 seeds of each rice strain screened were sown in 20-cm-long